

Skye Jurassic

When dinosaurs roamed Scotland

Image: Brachiosaurus on Skye (Credit: Open Virtual Worlds).

With its incredible range of animal and plant fossils, Skye is the dinosaur capital of Scotland. 161 to 176 million years ago, Middle Jurassic Skye was a subtropical island of beaches and lagoons. Hot, wet, and humid, it was occupied by a wide variety of flora and fauna. Surviving fossils also demonstrate the wide variety of plant life and existence of forests, valleys, and floodplains. This varied ecosystem featured herbivores, omnivores, and carnivores. Marine reptiles Ichthyosaurs and plesiosaurs, long-necked sauropods, three-toed theropods, duck-billed ornithopods, back-plated stegosaurs, turtles, crocodiles, and even mice-like mammals populated the area. Large and small dinosaurs ran on land or swam through the water. Other finds testify to the presence of flying reptiles. Middle Jurassic fossils are rare. As such, Skye offers unique insights into not just the dinosaurs of Scotland but of the whole Middle Jurassic period.

How Did We Know What to Reconstruct?

Fossils provide the majority of evidence about the middle Jurassic period. Plant, bones, and footprints remain embedded in the landscape. This includes finds indicating the presence of flying reptiles, dinosaur parenting, and milk-producing mammals. Excavated fossils are held at the Staffin Museum on Skye. Groupings of footprints by Duntulm Castle to the north and in Staffin Bay to the east form the largest collection of fossilised footprints in Scotland. In 2002, a storm revealed additional fossils near Staffin, which were then analysed by palaeontologists from the University of Glasgow. In 2015 and 2018, palaeontologists at the University of Edinburgh conducted studies on another set of footprints by Rubha nam Brathairean. Flora fossils also established Skye as having a Jurassic climate similar to Canada and Greenland, allowing for comparisons to be drawn.

How Was the Reconstruction Created?

A digital landscape was created using survey data and height map. Models were created in 3D modelling programs and imported into UNREAL (a cross-platform game engine for creating virtual worlds). The models were then scaled, orientated and assembled. The landscapes were populated with flora and fauna. Where applicable, models of characters and animals were imported and animated.

How Has the Reconstruction Been Used?

This project has been part of CUPIDO, a wider project, in conjunction with the AROS Centre, Skye. Together, these reconstructions tell the evolution of Skye in the 45 min film, 'SkyeStory'.

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How to Access the Reconstruction.

You can view a reconstruction of Jurassic era Skye on [Vimeo](#).

Full video available to view at the [AROS Centre](#), Portree, Skye, Scotland as part of the '[SkyeStory](#)'.

Discover More

Information about Skye can be found on [Canmore](#) CANMORE

More on the geology of Jurassic Skye can be found on [Wikipedia](#). **W**

You can see where the dinosaur footprints are located on [Google Maps](#).

Artefacts viewable at the [Staffin Museum](#).

Project Funding

This reconstruction was part of the [CUPIDO](#) (Culture Power: Inspire to Develop Rural Areas) project to develop new business opportunities in the cultural and cultural heritage sector around the North Sea, to reinforce the economic position, competitiveness and social cohesion of local rural communities in areas with a declining population. CUPIDO is co-funded by the North Sea Region Programme 2014-2020. The partnership has 14 partners from 7 regions in 6 countries around the North Sea.

CUPIDO is mainly about the commercialisation of the cultural sector that contributes towards creating vibrant, sustainable rural municipalities/communities that attract people to live, work and enjoy life. The project offers its partners an opportunity to jointly share resources, knowledge and expertise to commercialise the cultural sector. It enables insight into new business approaches, stimulates the development of products and services, and aims at an

average of five new start-ups per area and support to existing SME's. Follow CUPIDO in social media #cupidoNSR

Date Reconstruction Published: The digital representation of Skye Jurassic was produced in 2019.

The project is funded by the North Sea Region.